

QUAREP-LiMi By-Laws

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Preamble

The Consortium for Quality Assessment and Reproducibility for Instruments and Images in Light Microscopy (QUAREP-LiMi), formed by the global community of practitioners, researchers, developers, service providers, funders, publishers, policy makers and industry related to the use of light microscopy, is committed to democratizing access to quantitative and reproducible light microscopy and the data generated by it. Our mission is to provide a comprehensive set of community-agreed guidelines, protocols, automation procedures and other resources aimed at improving quality control, quality assurance, and instrument/method calibration. The stakeholders advocate for the use of the highest level of reproducibility for data generated by light microscopy methods in scientific research and biotechnology applications.

In support of achieving its mission, QUAREP-LiMi: 1) sanctions Working Groups to form teams that focus on specific technical or outreach topics; 2) maintains, disseminates, and teaches best practices, protocols, and software tools; and 3) collaborates with providers of reference materials or instrumentation or other tools that enable the easy implementation of best practices at the community-level.

QUAREP-LiMi was founded in 2020 and has since operated under an *ad hoc* consensus model. Beginning in 2022, discussions have repeatedly addressed the need to formalize the QUAREP-LiMi organizational structure and establish a means of legitimizing the decision-making process. These needs reflect the growth and success of QUAREP-LiMi. The creation of by-laws aims to ensure QUAREP-LiMi provides a diverse, equitable, inclusive, and transparent environment for its community to gather, address and efficiently make decision to address critical challenges, while protecting the integrity, value, and sustainability of the consortium.

QUAREP-LiMi is a volunteer organization. It is within the aims of QUAREP-LiMi to acquire funding for administrative and other activities. Hence, the by-laws are designed to account for both operational modes, whether relying exclusively on volunteers or a mixed model with volunteers and paid personnel. The aim is to maximize efficiency and transparency while minimizing the administrative burden of the operation.

The by-laws lay out the governing bodies of the consortium, their membership, and the processes by which members are elected or nominated for specific offices. The representative model hinges on balancing the contribution of active working group (WG) participants and general QUAREP-LiMi members, i.e., the “citizens” of the consortium. The activities carried out within the WGs represent the core of QUAREP-LiMi’s pursuit. As such, the WGs are meant to be self-organized, and to operate as it is best suited for their respective projects. WGs utilize teamwork and teamscience approaches to create technical sound and well-balanced work products in support of the mission

of QUAREP-LiMi. WGs shall hold elections for their co-chairs and nominate representatives from their membership to the governing committees.¹² The General Assembly (GA) is formed by all members of QUAREP-LiMi, both those who are active in WGs and those who are not.³ Members of

the GA vote⁴ to elect members of the governing committees at annual meetings by the rules set forth in these by-laws.⁵

¹ Every member of the consortium can choose to be active in a WG but does not have to. Members that belong to one or multiple WG(s) are eligible to participate in full in each WG and to take part in the nomination process of representatives for each WG. Activity in WG(s) does not impact voting rights in the GA.

² All governing committees operate in open session and every member of the consortium can attend and participate in committee meetings. Certain functions within these committees, as described in these by-laws, will be exclusive to elected or nominated members of these committees.

³ QUAREP-LiMi representation is based on a mixed model within which each QUAREP-LiMi member has equal voting rights in the GA. Members active in WGs can, in addition, participate in the nomination of representatives through their WG(s). Representation through vote of the GA and representation by nomination through a WG are not the same mechanism and not mutually exclusive.

⁴ There are two forms of votes that can be used to fulfill a voting requirement defined by the by-laws. These two forms are 1) a vote using a voting system and 2) acclamation. Acclamation must be unanimous and can only be taken if voting contingencies (quorum, percentage of membership, etc.) are met. Voting systems shall be provided by the steering committee (SC) and administered by the Annual Meeting Committee (AMC) for the GA, as well as upon request of any standing committee or Working Group (WG). If WGs plan to use voting systems that they self-administer, the voting system needs to be endorsed prior to the vote by the SC as documented in the Best Practices.

⁵ Elections can be held as needed if a GA is in session. The GA can be called into session outside of annual meetings as described in the by-laws and election can take place at such extraordinary called sessions of the

<p>Steering Committee (SC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 member per WG • N(WG)-1 elected members • Up to 3 statutory members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chair of ERB • Chair of OB • Chair of AMC • Non-voting members (e.g. OB-SC rep) <p>The SC elects 4 mandatory officers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-chair 1 • Co-chair 2 • Secretary • Treasurer <p>The SC forms the Executive Council (EC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9 members' total • 4 mandatory officers • Chair of AMC • 4 members elected among SC 	<p>Editorial Review Board (ERB)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 member per WG (voting) • OB ERB rep (non-voting) • No other elected members • ERB elects one chair who operates as editor in chief
	<p>Ombuds Board (OB)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 elected members (voting) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chair • SC rep • ERB rep • 1 member per WG (voting)
	<p>Annual Meeting Committee (AMC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chair • Volunteer members (any level of QUAREP-LiMi member) • AMC organizes Annual Meeting • AMC organizes Elections

Boards and Committees of the QUAREP-LiMi consortium. The operation of QUAREP-LiMi is coordinated through its Steering Committee (**SC**), which consists of representatives for the WGs, directly elected members, statutory members and any number of non-voting members, e.g. representatives of other community organizations, paid staff, etc. All voting members of the SC elect the mandatory officers and non-mandatory members of the Executive Council (**EC**). The EC acts between SC meetings, but must have its decisions confirmed by the SC. The Editorial Review Board (**ERB**) exclusively deals with the review, consortium wide feedback and communication of mature work products from the WGs. ERB members are representatives of WGs. The Ombuds Board (**OB**) is the mechanism by which each member can seek resolution to issues that need mediation. The OB is formed by representatives of the WGs; however, its chair and co-chairs are the only officers in the consortium that are directly elected by the GA. The Annual Meeting Committee (**AMC**) is organized by its chair, who is elected from

Being able to come to efficient and consensual decisions is pivotal for the function of a consortium like QUAREP-LiMi.⁶ As such, QUAREP-LiMi differentiates between decisions that concern the core mission of the consortium and operative decisions. **A)** Decisions that concern the core mission of the consortium – e.g., the generation of general content like metadata models, reference datasets, publications, and protocols, for Quality Assessment and Reproducibility – need to follow a consensus model, comparable to the operations of the International Standards Organization (ISO) and other similar standard organizations. Work products represent both the time commitment and reputation of the members that created them. At the same time, if released to the public in the name of the consortium, such products impact the professional reputation of all consortium members. To balance the protection of time that members invest into work products with the protection of the reputation of QUAREP-LiMi as well as its members the consensus model allows for two

principal outcomes: 1) full endorsement of a work product through the mechanisms provided in these by-laws or 2) endorsement as a discussion contribution if consensus for full endorsement cannot be reached.⁷

GA. Typically a voting period will flank time before and after a GA. The whole voting period (voting window) is sanctioned through calling the GA into session at a sanctioned meeting.

⁶ The ability to find consensus is the pillar for the function of team approaches in WGs and essential for any community-oriented project.

⁷ The designation of ‘discussion contribution’ provides a pathway for the consortium to value all work by its members, even if the work for example is too provocative to find consensus for full endorsement. The

B) Operative decisions⁸, for instance the sanctioning of new WGs, self-organization of the consortium through establishing a new office, reactions to community requests, etc. will be made based on consensus whenever possible, but utilization of voting is permitted if necessary.⁹

The need to make decisions and to endorse work products can lead to situations in which a member of the consortium needs recourse to efficiently voice comments, concerns or other input on a process, work product or other matter. The mechanism by which this need is addressed within QUAREP-LiMi is an Ombuds model.

These by-laws define the membership of QUAREP-LiMi and its representation through the GA and WG. They establish a Steering Committee (SC) – which forms within it the Executive Council (EC) – an Editorial Review Board (ERB), an Ombuds Board (OB) and an Annual Meeting Committee (AMC) as governing structures of the consortium. The SC can suggest changes to the by-laws to establish other Committees or Boards through approval by vote of the GA. QUAREP-LiMi, while not having initially any monetary value on its own other than the primary support for infrastructure through the founding members, has now been recognized by many supporting organizations (journals, institutions, standards institutes, funders, and instrumentation / software companies) – leading to the point that QUAREP-LiMi has become “something of significant value”. These by-laws aim to protect the integrity, value, and sustainability of the consortium.

The by-laws define other documents such as, for instance the Code of Conduct (CoC), Best Practices (BP) and Terms of Reference (ToR). These additional documents guide the operation of the consortium.¹⁰ The aim of introducing these by-laws as well as the spirit in which these by-laws shall be adjusted and extended going forward is to: 1) keep QUAREP-LiMi productive; 2) protect members’ time and reputation; 3) ensure the quality and consistency of work products; and 4) provide a productive path for all work products towards release.

underlying logic is that not every idea, not every concept is from its beginning ready to be the new state of the art. Indeed, many projects within the consortium will address areas that need to develop further and in the process work products will be created that should be released to the community to further the discussion of such topics. The endorsement of a work product as ‘discussion contribution’ allows release of such work. An example situation could be work products in areas that have not yet settled to the point that a consensus for full endorsement can be reached, or work products that challenge widely accepted paradigms.

⁸ Operative decisions are generally classified as decisions that support the function of the consortium without being directly related to the core topics of QUAREP-LiMi.

⁹ Votes are a necessary tool to operate and manage time and afford spend. They do result in “winners” and “losers” though and should therefore be used with care.

¹⁰ These guiding documents can be updated through unanimous acclamation or two-thirds majority vote of the SC, and if applicable will have to be developed and maintained with specific WGs, an example are ToRs that frequently will describe the work of WGs for internal and external reference and will have to be developed by each WG.

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The Mission of QUAREP-LiMi

The Consortium for Quality Assessment and Reproducibility for Instruments and Images in Light Microscopy (QUAREP-LiMi), *formed* by the global community of practitioners, researchers, developers, service providers, funders, publishers, policy makers and industry related to the use of light microscopy, is committed to democratizing access to quantitative and reproducible light microscopy and the data generated by it. Our mission is to provide a comprehensive set of community-agreed guidelines, protocols, automation procedures and other resources aimed at improving quality control, quality assurance, and instrument/method calibration. The stakeholders advocate for the use of the highest level of reproducibility for data generated by light microscopy methods in scientific research and biotechnology applications. In support of achieving its mission, QUAREP-LiMi: 1) sanctions Working Groups to form teams that focus on specific technical or outreach topics; 2) maintains, disseminates, and teaches best practices, protocols, and software tools; and 3) collaborates with providers of reference materials or instrumentation or other tools that enable the easy implementation of best practices at the community level.

Organizational Units of QUAREP-LiMi and their functions

Membership

Membership in QUAREP-LiMi is open without restriction to practitioners and other members of the light microscopy community globally. The term “light microscopy community” shall be interpreted broadly, inclusive of scientists and staff in academia and industry positions, as well as, for instance, members of publishing entities, regulators, funders, other communities, or community organizations and so on. Membership is established through registration on the quarep.org webpage¹¹ in the member section. Membership can be ended by each individual member through withdrawal from the membership list on the quarep.org webpage. Membership can be revoked as the outcome of mediation process by vote of the Ombuds Board (OB) and confirmation by the Steering Committee (SC) and Editorial Review Board (ERB).¹²

¹¹ Upon future changes to the representation formats of QUAREP-LiMi, the by-laws shall be updated as consequence of the approval process of any such changes. This means that if for instance a new web-address is established through due process in the SC the by-laws membership section can be updated without a vote of the GA.

¹² For the duration of a mediation process aiming to revoke membership the member under question shall have all privileges of membership other than a vote in the GA. Exceptions to this rule can be implemented by the OB if advocated for by the SC. Circumstances under which a further reduction of membership privileges could be justified include, but are not limited to examples of academic misbehavior, undue usage of consortium resources, for instance the illegitimate distribution of confidential information or data or other striking misbehavior.

General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) of QUAREP-LiMi represents all members of the consortium. The GA may be called into session at additional meetings.¹³¹⁴ Annual meetings shall be held virtually. This may include, but it is not limited to, streaming virtually from a physical location that has an “in-person” contingent of members, resulting in a combined physical and virtual annual meeting. The chair of the Annual Meeting Committee (AMC) shall act as chair of the GA as well as the annual meeting¹⁵ and be responsible for organizing elections and voting on other topics as sanctioned by the SC. Each QUAREP-LiMi member has an equal vote. The Steering Committee (SC) in consultation with the AMC,¹⁶ shall define the technical implementation of the voting process.¹⁷

Recognition of and Quorum for the GA

For a meeting of members of the consortium to be recognized as the GA, the meeting: 1) must be organized by the QUAREP-LiMi AMC, 2) must be sanctioned by the QUAREP-LiMi SC 3) must be announced at least 30 days before the assembly with an agenda duly distributed before the meeting but less than 30 days in advance, and 4) must meet a quorum of QUAREP-LiMi members in good standing.¹⁸ Quorum for the GA is set at 33% of active membership. Active membership is established by the average number of members attending WG meetings in the past six months, summed over all WGs active in that period and corrected for members that attend multiple WGs. This number is calculated by the AMC and announced before the GA is assembled at the (annual) meeting.¹⁹

¹³ The SC sanctions the annual meeting and approves its agenda. The AMC (annual meeting committee) is developing the agenda, running the annual meeting and elections. Any member can petition the SC or the AMC to bring a vote on a topic. If the necessary majority or unanimous support for the motion for such vote is met in the SC, the AMC shall add such approved topic to the annual meeting agenda.

¹⁴ To call the GA into session at additional meetings the SC must sanction such a meeting and the meeting must be organized by the AMC.

¹⁵ The GA can be called into session at an annual meeting or a meeting that meets the organizational requirements for sanction through the SC and organization through the AMC. An annual meeting can be held without active session of the GA, for instance if no voting is needed.

¹⁶ In cases there the SC and AMC do not agree on the type of vote to be called the outcome of the OB process shall be binding.

¹⁷ The decision on the appropriate voting mechanism shall be driven by the context of the voting topic. For instance, for the approval of a change to the by-laws a simple vote is appropriate, while for candidate election a ranked choice vote might be called for. If ranked choice voting is not supported in a voting platform other implementation strategy, for example multiple votes per member, might be chosen.

¹⁸ Good standing requires members to be properly registered as defined in the member section of the by-laws and to not be part of a mediation process that aims at revoking membership.

¹⁹ The AMC shall rely on the participant numbers reported by the WGs but have the authority to verify such numbers through meeting protocols, recordings, and other means. For votes the quorum can be established through all votes submitted during the voting window which can open prior to the meeting at which the GA is assembled and last until after the meeting has concluded.

Working Groups

Working groups (WG) constitute the fundamental operational unit of the QUAREP-LiMi consortium. WGs organize and perform the fundamental work of QUAREP-LiMi thus generating general content, metadata models, reference datasets, publications, tutorials, and protocols for Quality Assessment and Reproducibility, and other work products. WGs operate in team fashion and utilize the full breath of their members expertise and perspectives.

Working group rules

WGs operate under these general guidelines:

- WGs must be sanctioned by the Steering Committee (SC) and follow the QUAREP-LiMi Best Practices (BP)²⁰ and Terms of Reference (ToR)²¹ for organizing, holding meetings and documenting work progress, and adhere to the consortiums Code of Conduct (CoC).²²
- Establishing a new WG requires the demonstration of a need for the WG. It must be shown that an active²³ group of QUAREP-LiMi members will contribute to the WG. While there is no minimum member requirement, at least ten active members are typically expected. No WG shall be sanctioned by the SC that duplicates an existing WG or overlaps unduly. WGs can evolve from interest groups.²⁴
- WGs must elect co-chairs.²⁵ Additional WG-members may be elected or appointed^{26,27} as officers for other functions as needed. For instance, co-chairs may be unable to fulfill all

²⁰ In 2024 the BP are under development. BP are based on the methods employed by WGs from 2020 to 2023 and describe the nuts-and-bolts operational procedures for meeting planning, publication of meeting dates and documentation of meetings. The BP can be used to document secondary procedures and other best practices of the consortium as needed. The BP document is maintained and authored by the SC.

²¹ In 2024 the ToR is under development, it is maintained and authored by the SC in coordination with applicable WGs. WGs might decide to author ToRs for projects that will become part of the overall ToR through coordination with the SC.

²² In 2024 the CoC is under revision. The CoC describes the operational expectations for an open, inclusive and productive work environment within QUAREP-LiMi. The CoC document is maintained and authored by the SC.

²³ Activity is defined analogous to the GA quorum definition as: Activity is established by the average number of members attending interest group meetings either in the past six calendar months or since founding of the interest group.

²⁴ IGs are defined in the WG section of the bylaws.

²⁵ Typical functions and duties of co-chairs are defined in the BP.

²⁶ WGs are free to decide their mode of operation within the general framework governing QUAREP-LiMi. This includes their process for nominating members to governing committees and general decision making.

²⁷ There are two forms of vote that can be used to fulfill a voting requirement defined in the by-laws. These two forms are 1) a vote using a voting system and 2) acclamation. For a WG to appoint a member to a function or representation without a vote the conditions for acclamation must be met. Acclamation must be unanimous and can only be taken if voting contingencies (quorum, percentage of membership, etc.) are met. Voting systems shall be provided by the steering committee (SC) and administered by the Annual Meeting Committee (AMC) for the GA, as well as upon request of any standing committee or Working Group

functions typically assigned to the co-chairs.²⁸ In such case, the WG may nominate an additional member for specific functions, such as to represent the WG in one of the other organizational units of QUAREP-LiMi or to regularly perform a task that is necessary for the WG to function.

- Co-chairs serve a two-year term and may be re-elected. The term starts with the WG meeting at which the result of the vote is announced.²⁹
- Beyond the election of co-chairs and the election or nomination of officers, WGs may organize and operate as best serves their purpose.
- Membership in a WG is managed through quarep.org and membership in every WG is open to every QUAREP member.
- WGs must adhere to the conflict resolution process of QUAREP-LiMi if a situation cannot be addressed within the WG. WGs must respond to requests from the Ombuds Board (OB).³⁰
- A WG may be dissolved either by request of the WG or action by the SC if a WG either 1) is inactive beyond six months without requesting an extension, or 2) does not operate within the rules of the consortium. A unanimous vote by the full SC is necessary for the dissolution of a WG. By unanimous vote of the Executive Council (EC) of the SC, said EC may change the requirement of a unanimous vote to a two-thirds majority vote of the full SC in cases where one or more SC members are unresponsive or inactive. In exceptional circumstances³¹ the EC may seek approval from the OB to change the full SC vote temporarily to a two-thirds majority vote.

Interest Groups

Interest Groups (IG) can form spontaneously around topics of interest. IGs can form from one or multiple WGs or independent of WGs. IGs may be short lived, but if they exist for more than 6 months they need to be recognized by the SC. This is a formal step that does not normally require an approval process, nor should it be deniable. A recognized IG is obligated to function in accordance with WG rules as set forth in the by-laws and Best Practices document. Resolving a recognized IG follows the same rules as for WG but meets a lower bar than resolving a WG. Therefore an IG can be resolved through the SC by 2/3 majority vote.

(WG). If WGs plan to use voting systems, they self-administer the voting system needs to be endorsed prior to the vote by the SC and the outcome of the vote must be documented with the AMC.

²⁸ Typical functions and duties of co-chairs are defined in the BP.

²⁹ If the election results are disseminated by other means than a WG meeting, the election cycle starts with the first meeting of the WG after the election.

³⁰ The OB will typically contact WG chairs and individual members as needed, all of whom are obliged to respond in a reasonable timeframe, but typically within less than a week to requests by the OB.

³¹ Exceptional is defined as circumstance beyond the inability to get a response from a SC member.

Resolving a WG through action of the SC must meet a high bar, therefore, before a 2/3 vote is utilized several safety steps (EC in case of unresponsive SC members, or OB in extreme other conditions) must be taken.

Annual Meeting Committee

The annual meeting committee (AMC) organizes the annual meeting, its meeting agenda, and organizes elections for the GA and by request for WGs, boards and standing committees of the consortium. The chair of the AMC shall preside over the annual meeting. The chair of the AMC shall call into session the GA as set forth within the GA section and chair the GA while it is in session. Candidates for elections can self-nominate to the chair of the AMC. A member may nominate another member to the chair of the AMC but must present documentation that the nominated member agrees to the nomination. Candidates need to be endorsed by two members of the consortium.³² Endorsement will be requested by the AMC. Election results will be shared with candidates by the AMC and candidates need to accept their election prior to release of the election results to the consortium.³³

AMC membership is confirmed by the steering committee (SC) and open to all consortium members. The chair of the AMC should be an elected or appointed member of the SC, unless no SC member has the resources available to chair the AMC, in which case the SC can appoint a chair for the AMC who is not a member of the SC.³⁴

Steering Committee

The steering committee (SC) is responsible for the operation and organization of QUAREP-LiMi. The SC consists of the following voting members: 1 representative from each WG³⁵; plus N-1 directly

³² No member of the consortium shall nominate more than three candidates to the SC and no more than one candidate to the OB.

³³ Because there is a substantial amount of time between candidacy and election this provision is a courtesy to candidates. If a candidate does not reply to the AMC within 48h of the election result being sent the result will be viewed as confirmed. This provision is meant to help minimize early fluctuations within the SC by elected members dropping their mandate. If an elected candidate refuses the election outcome the candidate with the most votes that was not elected will fill the vacated spot. Candidates can only decline the outcome of being elected, not the outcome of not being elected.

³⁴ If the SC appoints a chair of the AMC who is not a member of the SC this impacts the composition of the SC and EC as the appointed chair of the AMC is still a statutory member of the SC and EC. If this provision results in an even number of voting members in the SC, the chair of the AMC shall recuse themselves from voting in the full SC if their vote would result in a 50/50 vote of the SC. This provision does not apply to the EC.

³⁵ If new WGs are formed between GA assemblies, the new WG immediately gains representation in the SC. At the next meeting at which a GA is in session an additional SC member can be elected if a candidate self-nominates or is nominated and agrees to the nomination. If this provision results in an even number of voting members in the SC, the new WG representative shall recuse themselves from voting in the full SC if their vote would result in a 50/50 vote of the SC.

elected members where N is the number of active WGs³⁶³⁷³⁸; plus up to three statutory members,³⁹ which are the chair of the Editorial Review Board, the chair of the Ombuds Board and the chair of the Annual Meeting Committee (AMC). The SC has mandatory non-voting members and can have additional non-voting members. Meetings of the SC are open to all members of the consortium, while voting is reserved for voting members of the SC.⁴⁰

The SC forms, by election or acclamation, an Executive Council (EC) that can enact fast responses on actions and topics that require so. The EC has five statutory members and four elected members that must be elected or appointed voting members of the SC.⁴¹

The SC must follow the applicable rules for WG operation, BP, ToR and CoC but does not constitute a WG within the consortium.

The SC has a defined quorum, however, due to the way that votes are structured⁴² the SC can meet without meeting quorum at the meeting while still initiate votes. If at the beginning of an SC meeting quorum is not reached procedural functions that require quorum of present members cannot be executed until quorum is reached.

Mission and Function

The operational and organizational function of the SC includes:

- Self-governance

³⁶ For example: If N is the number of existing WGs, (N-1) directly elected SC seats may be filled. By April 2024 the expectation is that 14 WGs (QUAREP-LiMi has 15 WGs but WG9 is excluded as it acts as the temporary SC) are active. The maximum number of SC members is therefore 27 (14 eligible WG nominees plus 13 directly elected candidates).

³⁷ The SC is ensured an odd number of members by electing one less direct member of the SC than there are WGs. This mechanism is also intended to counter the potential for undue influence in the consortium gained by the manipulation of membership as membership is open without conditions to practitioners and other members of the light microscopy community. If ever such a situation arises this provision shall guide its resolution.

³⁸ The SC is functional in that it can reach quorum with fewer than the maximum number of directly elected members. Indeed, it is intentional that a functional SC can be formed without a single directly elected member. This is meant as a mechanism to add robustness to the operation of the consortium. If a candidate for direct election is declared to the AMC an election must be held at the next regular meeting there a GA is in session (in other words within a maximum period of one year from declaration of candidacy, ideally as soon as possible).

³⁹ 'Up to three' refers to the possibility that the chair of the AMC is not originally a part of the SC, but appointed by the SC. There will always be at least two statutory members of the SC, which are the chairs of the ERB and OB.

⁴⁰ Non-voting members of the SC, including all consortium members can participate in SC meetings. The co-chairs of the SC may decide that speaking time is limited for non-voting members if necessary for practical reasons. In this case it falls to the chair of the AMC to ensure that non-voting members that wish to speak are recognized for a minimum of two minutes. This is the equivalent of a "public hearing" provision.

⁴¹ The EC is defined in the SC section of the by-laws.

⁴² See 'Procedures for vote' section in SC section of by-laws.

- Creation and Termination of WGs.
- Recognition of Interest Groups (IG).⁴³
- Creation of new committees.⁴⁴
- Other actions in the spirit of these by-laws as needed.
- Proposing any changes to the by-laws to the GA for approval by vote.⁴⁵
- Making Conflict of Interest determinations, other than those related to the ERB.⁴⁶
- Modifying the guidance documents like the Best Practices (BP), Terms of Reference (ToR) and Code of Conduct (CoC) documents.
- Issuing “Request for Comments” as described in the BP.
- Approving Best Practice level documents aimed at the community that are not intended to be submitted to journals for publications or have not yet reached the publication status.⁴⁷⁴⁸
- Approving the release of stable protocols.⁴⁹
- Sanction activities by members of the consortium in the name of the consortium.⁵⁰

For topics not listed above but that have a reasonable similarity to the topics in the list, the SC shall establish, if they fall within the purvey of the SC. If necessary, the ERB shall be consulted, and the by-laws updated as needed.

⁴³ IGs are defined as subsection of WGs.

⁴⁴ This implicitly includes the power to propose new boards and consortium wide governing committees such as a general advisory board or other boards/committees that may be necessary to operate legally. As such, the creation of a board or governing committee must be reflected in the by-laws. The rules for amending the by-laws would apply alongside such drastic changes, in contrast with smaller committees, for instance subcommittees of the SC, which may be created by the SC alone.

⁴⁵ The SC cannot alter the by-laws without review by the AMC and a vote at the GA. However, the SC controls the process for changing the by-laws and must initiate the process.

⁴⁶ The OB shall manage and resolve issues regarding conflict of interest related to the ERB.

⁴⁷ This process shall include a presentation by the WG(s) that developed the work product as well as any data the WG(s) have collected. This process shall also include determination of the consensus level within the WG on the work product and which level of endorsement, option A or B of the preamble, is appropriate.

⁴⁸ Approval shall follow the consensus model for manuscript endorsement under option A of the preamble. If an overlap with content that is either already submitted to the ERB or will likely be submitted to the ERB is found or argued for by any entity involved, the SC shall seek coordination with the ERB. “Entity” describes any member of the SC, any member related to the work product, ombuds or any other member of the consortium. If the level of the work product submitted is discussed for endorsement by the SC or the ERB, the relation of utility patents to design patent (equivalent to the small and large coin in German patent law) shall be utilized with work products most similar to the small coin being directed to the SC and work products most similar to the large coin being directed to the ERB.

⁴⁹ Provisions for the approval of Best Practice work products shall be applied accordingly.

⁵⁰ For instance, endorse interviews, workshops, conference contributions, marketing materials and similar activities that state to represent QUAREP-LiMi. Frequently such activities will first be endorsed by the related WGs, and final approval will be provided by the SC or EC.

Mandatory Offices

The SC has the following four mandatory officers: 1&2) two co-chairs⁵¹, 3) the secretary, 4) the treasurer.

Co-chairs

The co-chairs shall organize the SC in a manner like the functions of WG chairs.⁵²

Secretary

The secretary shall organize SC meetings, oversee the agenda and minutes, and ensure that meetings are held according to the by-laws, CoC, BP and ToR as applicable.

Treasurer

The treasurer shall oversee book-keeping, budget plans and fund raising.⁵³

Chair of the AMC

The chair of the AMC shall be appointed from within the SC and fulfill the functions of the AMC as described in the AMC section, with the exceptions provided within it.

Non-voting members

The mandatory non-voting member of the SC is the Ombudsperson for the SC. Additional non-voting members may be named and confirmed by the SC. Examples are administrators, representatives of other boards as defined in the basic organizational units, representatives from other organizations, and so on. Non-voting members shall be included in all SC communications and invitations.

⁵¹ Because holders of mandatory offices by default belong to the EC only two co-chairs are mandatory. If more co-chairs are elected, the two co-chairs with the highest number of votes will belong to the EC. The co-chairs can unanimously agree on another solution as long as only two co-chairs of the SC are statutory members of the EC. If an additional co-chair also holds another mandatory office, it supersedes the 'number of co-chairs provision' as does election or acclamation by the full SC.

⁵² The co-chairs of the SC are in their every respect similar to WG chairs, with the only difference being that voting membership of the SC is governed by these by-laws. Explicitly the co-chairs of the SC are not meant to be the "chairs-of-chairs" or the assigned "leaders" of the consortium. The consortium is represented through its work products, the SC and in extension the EC with the understanding that consortium feedback is always solicited.

⁵³ While QUAREP-LiMi has no monetary value it does have cost for licenses and infrastructure that need to be met via sponsoring by its members. The treasurer oversees such contracts and see to their timely discussion in the SC.

Further organization

The SC self-organizes. To do so, it may create additional offices and sub-committees as needed.⁵⁴ The SC, through vote by two thirds of its members, can initiate its re-constitution at any time, but not more than twice a calendar year.⁵⁵

Executive Council

The SC forms an Executive Council (EC) either by election or acclamation by all members of the SC.⁵⁶ The EC consists of nine (9) members that may hold other offices within the SC. Two co-chairs,⁵⁷ the SC secretary, the treasurer and the chair of the AMC are statutory members of the EC and four EC members get elected from within the SC.⁵⁸ The function of the EC is to allow for fast responses on actions and topics that require so.⁵⁹ The EC may meet via conference calls⁶⁰ or through other electronic methods.⁶¹ EC decisions require a simple majority. EC decisions must be presented to the full SC at the next SC meeting for endorsement or correction.

⁵⁴ For instance, specific coordinators for industry members, other community initiatives (like national Bioluminescence consortia, ISO and similar) or WGs that service the consortium (like WG 7 (Metadata) and WG 8 (Education)); account manager; PR coordinator and other offices can be established.

⁵⁵ Re-constitution means that all mandatory offices are opened for a new vote, as well as the four elected members of the EC. If the SC has created non-mandatory offices these offices can be excluded from re-constitution by the same two thirds vote. This mechanism is meant primarily as a reprieve in case the EC is unresponsive to SC committee input, or the EC repeatedly fails to gain approval for decision made within its mandate.

⁵⁶ Apart from re-constitution within the SC, the formation of the SC and or the EC can only be challenged through the Ombuds process for 90 days after formation. A challenge does not impact function of the SC and or EC unless it is imposed by the OB by two third majority of its active membership.

⁵⁷ If more than two co-chairs exist, the two co-chairs with the most votes from the SC will be the statutory members of the EC unless the co-chairs agree on another solution. Other co-chairs might be EC members if elected/assigned by acclamation by the full SC or they hold another mandatory office that sanctions statutory EC membership.

⁵⁸ The SC must name four non-statutory members of the EC from within the SC. If unanimous acclamation fails, a vote using voting software, or another fair documentation process shall be used. Such vote shall be cast as a secret ballot to minimize peer-pressure on SC members.

⁵⁹ Examples of instances for which fast responses are required are responses to press requests; procedural decisions that the SC is expected to broadly support and are intended to move faster than the regular SC meeting schedule; and general “nuts and bolts” decisions for which confirmation by the SC at the next meeting can be reasonably expected.

⁶⁰ For instance, via Zoom.

⁶¹ In other words, a decision can be coordinated by email or similar means, but must be documented by at least one of the co-chairs of the SC/EC.

Quorum

Quorum is established by ten (10) SC members. Of these ten members, at least five (5) EC members must be present.⁶²

Procedures for votes

The primary process for decision making is unanimous acclamation after a consensus is reached.⁶³ Voting is intended for use as a secondary process predominantly for operational decision making to avoid delays. Votes of the full SC shall be cast by the following process:

- A motion for discussion of a topic is made and seconded by another SC member.
- The topic of the vote is discussed.
- A motion to vote is made and seconded.
- Voting takes place by a documentable process⁶⁴ by which every SC member, present at the meeting or not, can vote.⁶⁵ The ballot shall remain open until 48h before the next SC meeting.⁶⁶
- At the next SC meeting, the result of the vote is stated.
- A motion for additional debate is made.
 - If the motion is not seconded, the vote is hereby confirmed.
 - If the motion is seconded,
 - Additional debate is held.
 - A motion for a re-vote is made at the end of the debate.
 - If the motion is supported by at least 50% of SC members present at the meeting and the meeting attendance meets quorum requirements, a new vote will be held.
 - If the motion for a re-vote is not seconded, the vote is hereby confirmed.

If a preliminary decision is needed at the time of the first debate, the co-chair(s) can move to allow an EC vote on the topic. Unless this motion is opposed by a simple majority of SC members

⁶² In other words, the EC alone cannot constitute quorum for the SC, at least one other SC member needs to be present. There is an expectation that quorum will be met regularly. Such expectation is based on the WG9 attendance from 2020-2023.

⁶³ Votes may result in “winners” and “losers” and shall therefore be used with caution.

⁶⁴ For example, voting software, email send to chairs, recording of the vote of each SC member present at the SC meeting in the meeting minutes.

⁶⁵ To do so, an email shall be sent to all SC members announcing the vote. Such email shall reference the discussion documentation in the meeting agenda and indicating the method of voting.

⁶⁶ Unless a request for extension to vote is submitted, failure to submit a vote is counted as abstention. Such requests may be made by an SC member due to planned unavailability or on behalf of an SC member because of unplanned availability.

present at the SC meeting and the meeting attendance meets quorum requirements, such motion by the chair(s) shall be granted and remain in effect until the topic is resolved by vote of the full SC.

Editorial Review Board

Mission and Scope

The Editorial Review Board (ERB) is charged to facilitate coordination of work products at the level of scientific publications and other major work products.⁶⁷ The ERB provides WGs with a timely, and direct feedback mechanism.⁶⁸ The outcome of an ERB review shall consist of 1) feedback to the WG about maturity of their work; 2) a written review that the WG can decide to use to improve the work product; 3) an endorsement of work products as either “Discussion Level” (an important contribution to an area that is still in development or that challenges established views) or “Full Endorsement” (a contribution that aligns across QUAREP-LiMi and provides an important contribution to the field). Additionally, WGs can ask the ERB for 4) a letter to the editor to accompany the WGs work product at submission to a journal. The letter may contain the ERB review of the work product as attachments.

Membership, Operation and Procedures

Membership

The ERB is formed through nominations of one member per WG and an elected ombudsperson.⁶⁹ The ERB is operational⁷⁰ if four WGs have nominated a member to the ERB. ERB members serve a one-year term and can be re-nominated by their WG.⁷¹ WGs are asked to prioritize nominating members that have experience as reviewers for journals or are/were active editors at journals. No member of the consortium shall be nominated to the ERB by more than one WG, thereby term limits apply to the individual member.⁷² Former ERB reviewers can offer to serve the ERB through special case reviews at the discretion of the chair.

⁶⁷ The distinction between a work product being endorsed by the SC vs. the ERB is the level of complexity and scope of the release to the public. Manuscripts aimed at Journals shall be reviewed by the ERB before endorsement, while invited smaller contributions, comments, or similar publishable products may be endorsed by the SC if the WG(s) presenting the work product can demonstrate that consensus was reached. If a WG or the SC has doubts regarding the appropriate endorsement pathway, they shall reach out to the chair or the ERB, who – after consultation with the co-chairs of the SC – shall determine the appropriate endorsement pathway.

⁶⁸ Timely feedback with limited time demands on the WG is a major reason to establish the ERB through the by-laws.

⁶⁹ The SC does not nominate a member to the ERB.

⁷⁰ The ERB does not make determinations by vote (other than on a chair, if needed). Therefore, the ERB does not have a formal quorum.

⁷¹ While no formal term limit is set, it is expected that most reviewers will rotate through the ERB within 3–5 years.

⁷² For instance, if member A is nominated by WG-X the term is applied to member A. Nomination of member A by WG-Y shall not reset the term limit. Term limits shall reset after absence from the ERB for a year.

Operation

The ERB shall operate in observance of the CoC, BP and ToR of the consortium. First and foremost, the ERB's function is to serve the consortium, as is reflected in ERB review outcomes – no decisions are forced by the ERB other than mediating an endorsement level through consensus.

Scope of review and review criteria

To guide the review process and have a common framework for review, the ERB shall list its current guidelines for review in form of a Best Practice document on the QUAREP-LiMi cloud.

Chair and chairs obligation

Among the members of ERB, a chair or editor-in-chief is established either by consensus or an election.⁷³ The chair(s) of the ERB serve(s) a three-year term and may be nominated for a second term.⁷⁴ At the beginning of the ERB chair(s)' third year, either "chair(s) elect" shall be nominated by the members of the ERB unless the sitting chair(s) requests a second term and the members of the ERB agree to a second term. In the latter case, chair(s) elect shall be determined at the beginning of the sixth year. Confirmation of the chair(s) elect as new chair is established by a simple majority vote of the ERB members at the beginning of the new term. If a chair elect is not confirmed, the ERB must go through the initial process of agreeing on a chair. In such case, the chair elect shall not be excluded as a candidate. The chair is responsible for:

- Organizing regular monthly ERB meetings at which submitted work products are discussed and assigned for review.
 - If seasonal breaks are scheduled, the chair is responsible for scheduling an extraordinary ERB meeting or, if that proves impossible, to recruit two reviewers within two weeks of a work product being submitted to ERB.
- Reading work products that are submitted up to two weeks ahead of a regularly scheduled ERB meeting and to present those work products to the ERB for discussion and review assignment.
- Follow up with reviewers regarding timely submission of reviews.
- Check reviews for general fairness and helpfulness before sending them to the WG.
- Lobby WGs to nominate a member to ERB.
- Discussing grievances with the WG(s) that submitted a work product and/or the ERB ombuds.
- The chair of the ERB is a voting member of the SC but cannot be a member of the EC.

⁷³ The ERB can decide to utilize the co-chair model of the consortium but can be operational with a single chair.

⁷⁴ The tenure of any chair of the ERB shall be limited to 6 years (two full, consecutive terms) at a time. Term limits shall reset after a year of absence from the ERB. By 2/3 majority vote of the SC and OB an ERB chairs term might be extended if ERB is unable to produce a new chair. This provision shall be used rarely.

Member obligation

WG members that accept representation of their WG on the ERB become reviewers on the ERB. As reviewers they agree to:

- Attend regular and extra-ordinary ERB meetings as best as they can with an expected attendance rate of at least 75%.⁷⁵
 - If a reviewer is temporarily unable to meet the 75%-time requirement, the chair may agree to a limited time exception.
 - If a reviewer is regularly unable to meet the time requirement, the reviewer is expected to step down from the ERB.
 - The chair may ask a reviewer to step down if the time requirement is regularly not met or significantly fewer assignments are accepted by that reviewer than by the average reviewer on the ERB.
- Review work products within four (4) weeks of assignment.
- Accept work products for review on a regular and frequent basis.
- Respond to the chair of the ERB in a timely and helpful manner.
- ERB members may seek other roles within the consortium, including the SC. ERB members shall declare conflicts of interests that arise through their participation in other such roles. It is expected that the reviewer prioritizes the ERB over these other roles.⁷⁶

Conflict of Interest

If either an ERB member or its chair finds themselves in a situation where they recognize a conflict of interest (COI), they shall disclose so to the whole ERB. If a determination of COI is necessary, the OB co-chair for the ERB shall make an initial determination. In case either party requests so the ERB chair shall approach the chair of the Ombuds Board. A reviewer that was nominated by the submitting WG automatically has a COI and shall not handle or review the submitted work product.

Other Grievances

If a WG feels that the review has faults, procedural or content-wise, the WG shall voice these grievances to the ERB chair. If the WG deems the chair's response is insufficient, the WG shall ask for mediation by the co-chair of the OB for the ERB. If no mediation is possible, the WG shall approach the Ombuds Board chair for a full OB review.

⁷⁵ The reference time frame is a nine (9) calendar month year, like the academic year.

⁷⁶ The OB co-chair for the ERB shall be the first instance to clarify conflict of interest situations. If either the ERB member or the OB- co-chair for the ERB require so the full OB may be asked to evaluate a conflict of interest situation.

Ombuds Board

Mission and scope

Within QUAREP-LiMi every member is valued for their unique knowledge and perspective. No single member can be present at all meetings within the QUAREP-LiMi consortium, which might result in a situation where a mechanism is required to expediate the escalation of a concern. Additionally, within a consortium of the size of QUAREP-LiMi, we will find members advocating for opposing perspectives, approaches, and solutions. While our code of conduct aims to facilitate an open and honest exchange of thoughts, it is likely that occasional situations will arise that require mediation.

Utilizing the model of Ombudsmen allows a fast escalation of concerns, provides the opportunity to utilize a spokesperson to minimize barriers to escalating a concern, and provides a framework for the mediation of conflict within QUAREP-LiMi.

The Ombuds board (OB) and its members shall represent any member of the consortium that requests representation. They shall seek to mediate situations identified by the member that sought representation. The OB and its chair may seek additional help for mediation in the form of a SME (Subject Matter Expert) or others as they deem helpful. The full OB may close a case if either a consensus solution is found, i.e., the parties agree that the situation/case is resolved or, if no resolution can be found, decide on the case/situation. Such a determination shall occur after the presentation of the situation/case by the OB member directly handling the representation, listening to the member seeking representation, giving due process to any other party involved in the situation and consulting with SMEs as advocated for by the handling OB member. The OB member shall act in the best interest and in representation of the member that sought out the OB.⁷⁷ The OB shall seek a balanced position founded primarily on facts and expertise as is applicable and guided by the best interest for all participants involved in a case/situation as well as the consortium overall. For conflicts concerning the operation of the consortium determinations of the OB may be binding.

For the use within QUAREP-LiMi we will use Ombudsperson(s) instead of Ombudsman or Ombudsmen and refer to the organized group of Ombudspersons as Ombuds Board.

Ombuds Board

The Ombuds Board (OB) consists of three directly elected members, the chair, a dedicated Ombudsperson for the SC (a non-voting member of the SC), and a dedicated Ombudsperson for

⁷⁷ If the OB member concludes that representation is not in the best interest of the QUAREP member seeking representation or mediation, for instance the OB member concludes that the person seeking help holds a factually faulty position or is not acting honestly or representation for another reason is not in the persons best interest, the OB member shall consult with the full OB on an ad-hoc basis ASAP. The full OB shall seek a determination on representation and if the initially assigned OB member is best suited to handle the case or another OB member should be assigned or if the situation does not justify mediation.

the ERB (a member of the ERB⁷⁸), as well as nominated members from the WG. Each WG shall nominate one of its members to serve on the OB. The OB is functional upon determination of the three elected members. The OB can meet and operate synchronous⁷⁹ or asynchronous.⁸⁰ All members of the OB are considered (non-voting) members of every WG and committee of the consortium while mediating conflict.

Membership

Unlike any other Board in the consortium, the leadership of the OB is directly elected by the GA. The OB may have members in addition to the three elected members, one from each WG, administrative members and (temporary) advisory members from within or outside of the consortium. Administrative members and temporary members are appointed by the chair of the OB.

Elected members of the OB serve two-year terms and may seek re-election.⁸¹ Any member of the consortium can self-nominate for election to the OB.⁸² To do so, they must declare their candidacy to the chair of the AMC. Nominated members of the OB shall be re-nominated annually by their WG. Appointed members of the OB serve for as long as appointed by the chair of the OB but need to be officially re-appointed annually. Administrative members of the OB do not engage in OB functions and do not have term limits.

All members of the OB shall aim to attend at least 50% of regular meetings and be available for ad-hoc meetings as requested by the chair of the OB.⁸³

Members of the OB may step down at any time for any reason. If an elected member of the OB steps down, the chair shall temporarily assume their duties and actively seek out candidates for vote at the next GA.

⁷⁸ ERB functions without voting, therefore the OB-ERB rep is not labeled as ‘non-voting’.

⁷⁹ For instance, via Zoom.

⁸⁰ This means that a decision may be coordinated by email or other means.

⁸¹ No term limit is imposed with the expectation that an elected OB member or any OB member that is not appreciated by the consortium’s membership will likely resign. If an elected member of the OB needs to be removed and removal is contested by that OB member the full OB shall vote to trigger the following process: by simple majority of votes of the OB a not-contested elected member of the OB shall take the situation to the chair of the ERB and the co-chairs of the SC. If they cannot mediate a solution the full SC and full ERB can vote for removal for which a two third majority is needed in both the ERB and SC. If the need for removal does not originate from within the OB it has first be brought to the OB and adopted by a simple majority of OB members. An example for need of removal could be if the chair of the OB appoints enough external members under the discretion of the office to manipulate the function of the OB.

⁸² Endorsement by two consortium members applies.

⁸³ The time reference is a nine (9) calendar month year like the academic year. The chair of the OB can ask nominated members to seek replacement within their WG if they fail to contribute to the OB on a regular basis and this assessment is shared by the two others directly elected OB members.

Chair's Duties and Powers

The chair of the OB has the following duties and powers.

- The chair is entitled to ask any member of the consortium for information, their role in a process and their perspective on a situation.
- The chair receives grievances from members of the consortium.
- The chair may assign tasks to themselves or other members of the OB.
- The chair organizes regular OB meetings, which typically occur every 3 months, and ad-hoc meetings as needed.
- The chair and members of the OB that were assigned a task by the chair are empowered to seek out parties to a problem and attempt mediation.
- The chair may appoint temporary members to the OB.
- For matters concerning the SC or ERB, the chair shall refer to the elected Ombudspersons for these specific committees. If no such person is currently elected, the chair shall temporarily act as their replacement.
- The chair cannot deny candidacies for elected functions on the OB.

Conflict of Interest

If a member of the OB identifies a Conflict of Interest (Col) or a member of the consortium describes what can be reasonably perceived as a Col, the OB shall assign an ombudsperson that has no Col in the matter. If the Col concerns the chair of the OB, the full OB can temporarily assign one of its members as acting chair for matters related to the situation for which the Col exist. In such case, the elected OB chair remains the active chair in all other aspects of the OB.

Other Grievances

If the OB deadlocks, the chair of the OB shall seek out the chair(s) of the SC as mediators until the OB becomes functional.

Changes to the by-laws

Changes to the bylaws shall be initiated by the SC. The proposed change must be added by the AMC⁸⁴ to the meeting agenda of a meeting at which a GA is in session and voted on by the GA. If a chair or co-chair of the OB raises a concern the vote must be delayed until the next qualifying session of the GA.⁸⁵

Mandatorily elected office holders in executive committees of QUAREP-LiMi

At minimum, the following offices shall have elections for officers through the GA:

- Directly elected members of the SC
- The chair of the OB
- The ombudsperson for the SC
- The ombudsperson for the ERB

Exclusion rules for multiple office holders

Due to the volunteer nature of QUAREP-LiMi, it is assumed that some members of the consortium will assume multiple offices or functions described in the by-laws. With growth of the consortium, generally, multiple office or function holders shall consider reducing the number of offices or functions held if other candidates are available.

The following offices or functions are mutually exclusive:

- A co-chair of the SC shall not chair the OB or ERB.
- The chair of the OB shall not be the chair of any WG or the AMC.
- The chair of the AMC shall not hold any other mandatory office within the SC.
- No single person shall occupy more than one of the mandatory offices of the SC.⁸⁶

The following relations between serving on the governing committees of the consortium and WG activities apply:

- Chairs of the SC and ERB may serve as WG co-chairs and may take on any role within WGs.
- The chair of the OB shall not be the chair of any WG.
- The chair of the AMC may serve as chair of the ERB.

⁸⁴ The AMC shall only add proposed changes that have been agreed upon by the SC.

⁸⁵ The same change can only be delayed once through the Ombuds process, but the same change shall not be reintroduced for a vote before the OB has concluded through either a resolution to the concern or finding by the OB that the concern cannot be reasonably justified.

⁸⁶ This provision exists because such a situation would impact the function of the EC.

Mandatory nominations or elections within WGs

The following office holders within a WG must be established by vote:

- A minimum of two (2) co-chairs

The following office holders within a WG may be established by unanimous acclamation or vote:

- Reviewer for the ERB
- Ombudsperson to serve of the OB
- Content and model coordinator⁸⁷

Other General Provisions

- Every member of the consortium who is in good standing and does not carry a CoI shall principally be considered for every office in the consortium if the member so chooses.
- Members that serve on governing committees, boards or in WG may step down from their service for any reason at any time. If the member agreed to co-chair or hold another office with term limits or the need for an election to take place to replace them, they are asked to organize their leave in the most productive way possible.
- All committees and boards are structured such that there are more and less involved ways of contributing to allow a wide range of members to contribute.

⁸⁷ Many if not most WGs will touch metadata and documentation questions in their work, which will require coordination with the QUAREP-LiMi wide metadata schema. Schema editing and content curation needs to be supported by the WG that proposes changes to the master-schema. For more details refer to the BP document.